

**A STUDY OF ADJUSTMENT OF ADOLESCENT GIRLS IN RELATION
TO THEIR LEVEL OF INTELLIGENCE**

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ABSTRACT

The focus of the present society is on women empowerment. At that time this study is of utmost relevance as it is studying the adjustment of Adolescent Girls in relation to their Level of Intelligence. The study has been conducted on a sample of 100 Adolescent Girls senior secondary schools of Bahadurgarh city. Random sampling technique was used. The data was analyzed statistically by using mean, s.d. and 'z' score. The study revealed that Adolescent Girls with high intelligence are better adjusted as compared to Adolescent Girls with low intelligence in total adjustment and same is the case in emotional adjustment, social adjustment and educational adjustment.

Key words : Adjustment, Adolescent Girls, Level of Intelligence

The relationship which becomes established among the biological heritage or organism, the environment and the personality is adjustment. The adjustment process is a universal sequence that can be identified in the behavior of organism from the lowest species up to man. Life is a continuous process of adjustment in the present age, life is full of challenges and competitions. Students face problems of adjustment in various areas like social, emotional, vocational, school, health, home etc. To meet standards of the society, family, friends one has to try constantly to fit in the roles assigned by society. Many times these standards are met and a person in such situation is said to be well adjusted and at times tensions and conflicts lead to emotionality, socially, educationally unstable person. Intelligence, which makes a

person act accordingly and as per his capacities. Intelligence may be understood to be a mental energy available with an individual which enables him/her to cope with environment in terms of adaptation and dealing with novel situations as effectively as possible. Since adolescence is a stage which brings heightened sensitivity to sexual and social demands, educational demands of parents from their children, these all leads to many conflicts.

Jamuna D (2011) studied some factors related to adjustment of middle aged and older women and it was observed that middle aged and older women differed significantly in their levels of adjustment.

Bhatia, K.T (2004) finds that adolescents were some times treated like adults and some times like children, it was found that family atmosphere was more tense and unhappy for girls in the Indian environment.

Kumari, Sushma (2009) studied personality characteristics, intelligence, achievement, motivation, adjustment and socio-economic status of juvenile and adult female offenders. Finding was delinquents had low intelligence and achievement motivation, offenders were generally from the lower class of socio economic status except urban juvenile delinquents who belonged to middle category of socio economic status. offenders were maladjusted in all the areas of adjustment. Looking into these, we can say girls in Indian scenario face this pressure more than boys because of societies orthodox views, in such a condition a study of adjustment in adolescent girls of low and high intelligence becomes imperative.

Statement of the problem

A study of adjustment of Adolescent Girls in relation to their Level of Intelligence.

Operational definitions of the key terms used

ADJUSTMENT

According to Shaffer, "Adjustment is the process by which a living organism maintains a balance between its needs and the circumstances that influence the satisfaction of these needs." In the present study adjustment refers to the total score obtained by adolescent girl students in the AISS by Dr. A.K.P. Sinha and Dr. R.P. Singh.

INTELLIGENCE

According to Benet, “Ability of individual to direct his behaviour towards a goal.” In the present study intelligence refers to the total score obtained by adolescent girl students in Group mental ability test by S.S. Jalota.

ADOLESCENCE

According to Jersild, “Adolescence is that age when a child achieves maturity, it starts at the end of childhood and ends before adulthood.” In the present study adolescent girl refers to the girl students studying in 11th class.

Objectives of the study

- To compare the Total Adjustment of Adolescent Girls with low and high intelligence.
- To compare the Emotional Adjustment of Adolescent Girls with low and high intelligence.
- To compare the Social Adjustment of Adolescent Girls with low and high intelligence.
- To compare the Educational Adjustment of Adolescent Girls with low and high intelligence.

HYPOTHESIS

- There is significant difference in Total adjustment of Adolescent Girls with low and high intelligence.
- There is no significant difference in Emotional adjustment of Adolescent Girls with low and high intelligence.
- There is no significant difference in Social adjustment of Adolescent Girls with low and high intelligence.
- There is no significant differences in Educational adjustment of Adolescent Girls with low and high intelligence.

METHOD

A descriptive survey method was used in the study.

SAMPLE

The sample for this study consisted of 100 Adolescent Girls of Sr. Sec. Schools of Bahadurgarh city on the basis of random sampling technique.

Tools Used

Group mental ability test (1972) By S.S. Jalota

AISS By Dr. A.K.P. Sinha and Dr. R.P. Singh

Variables

Independent – Intelligence

Dependent – Adjustment

Statistic Technique

Mean, Standard deviation, and 'z' score were used to analyze the data.

Results and interpretation

Means, S.D. and 'z' of Total adjustment of Adolescent Girls with low and high intelligence.

Category	Mean	S.D.	'z' score	Level of Significance	
				0.05	0.01
Low Intelligence Girls	22.02	3.84	21.15	1.96	2.58
Highly Intelligence Girls	8.48	2.44		Significant	

Objectives of the study

To compare the total adjustment of Adolescent Girls with low and high intelligence.

Hypothesis : There is no significant difference in total adjustment of Adolescent Girls with low and high intelligence.

Interpretation : Table 1.1 depicts the means, S.D. and 'z' score of high intelligence and low intelligence adolescents on total adjustment. The mean score of high intelligence adolescents ($M = 8.48 \pm 2.44$) is lower than the mean score of low intelligence adolescents ($M = 22.02 \pm 3.84$). The 'z' value i.e. 21.15 is significant at 0.01 level of significance. The results indicate that high intelligent adolescents are more adjusted than low intelligent adolescents. Since the inventory is reverse scored. Therefore, low score indicate better adjustment and vice-versa.

Mean, S.D. and 'z' of Emotional adjustment of Adolescent Girls with low and high intelligence

Category	Mean	S.D.	'z' score	Level of Significance	
				0.05	0.01
Low Intelligence Girls	6.8	1.94	14.30	1.96	2.58
Highly Intelligent Girls	2.08	1.38		Significant	

Objective : To compare the Emotional Adjustment of Adolescent Girls with low and high intelligence.

Hypothesis : There is no significant difference in Emotional adjustment of Adolescent Girls with low and high intelligence.

Interpretation : Table 1.2 depicts the means, S.D. and 'z' of high intelligence and low intelligence adolescents on social adjustment. The mean score of high intelligence adolescents ($M = 4.3 \pm 1.33$) is lower than the mean score of low intelligent adolescents ($M = 9.5 \pm 2.04$). The 'z' value i.e. 15.29, is significant at 0.01 level of significance. The results indicate that high intelligent adolescents are more adjusted than low intelligent adolescents. Since the inventory is reverse scored. Therefore, low score indicate better adjustment and vice-versa.

Means, S.D. and 'z' of educational adjustment of Adolescent Girls with low and high intelligence

Category	Mean	S.D.	'z' score	Level of Significance	
				0.05	0.01
Low Intelligent Girls	6.44	1.72	14	1.96	2.58
Highly Intelligent Girls	2.1	1.41		Significant	

Objective : To compare the Social Adjustment of Adolescent Girls with low and high intelligence.

Hypothesis : There is no significant difference in Educational adjustment of Adolescent Girls with low and high intelligence.

Interpretation : Table 1.3 depicts the means, S.D. and 'z' value of high intelligence and low intelligence adolescents on educational adjustment. The mean score of high intelligence adolescents ($M = 2.1 \pm 1.41$) is lower than the mean score of low intelligent adolescents ($M 6.44 \pm 1.72$). The 'z' value i.e. 14, is significant at 0.01 level of significance. The results indicate that high intelligent adolescents are more adjusted than low intelligence adolescents. Since the inventory is reverse scored. Therefore, low score indicate better adjustment and vice-versa.

FINDINGS

The Adolescent Girls with high intelligence are better adjusted as compared to Adolescent Girls with low intelligence in total adjustment and same is the case in emotional adjustment, social adjustment and educational adjustment.

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